

FIBRE REINFORCED CONCRETE: PULL-OUT TESTS UNDER QUASI-STATIC AND HIGH-SPEED LOADING

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1 Introduction

Concrete is a brittle material with a low energy absorption capacity. Traditionally, fibres are used to enhance the fracture toughness by fibre pull-out after matrix failure. The mechanical behaviour of concrete composites is mostly described by quasi-static conditions which is fully sufficient for various applications. However, many structures are subjected to high-speed loads that might implement different failure mechanisms. The highest fracture energies at high strain rates are expected for multi-scale plastic deformation of the specimen before ultimate failure [1].

In the fibre reinforced concrete three different phases, namely cementitious matrix, fibre and their interphase, have to be considered when describing the material behaviour. Since the stress is transferred from matrix to fibre by the interphase, a detailed understanding of the complex mechanism of fibre/matrix interaction is a precondition for the improvement of the mechanical behaviour of concrete composites under impact. For concrete structures it is essential to improve the toughness at high strain rates by adaption of the interphase properties. First of all, the mechanism of the interphase failure at different strain rates has to be evaluated. However, little research has been done to understand the fibre/matrix bond under impact.

Micromechanical pull-out tests on single fibre model composites are an established way to characterize the mechanical properties of the interphase [2]. An embedded fibre end is quasi-statically pulled out of a matrix droplet and the

force-displacement curve is determined. At the micro level, interfacial interaction is usually described in terms of various parameters which characterize load transfer through the interphase: bond strength, interfacial shear stress, critical energy release rate of the interface, etc. [3, 4].

Also non-destructive measurements are used permitting cyclic loading of a single fibre model composite with frequencies varying in the range of 10–350 Hz, where only the force and phase shift between excitation and resulting force are determined [5]. Another device was built up for measuring hysteresis curves (force as a function of displacement). Therefore, end-embedded single fibre model composites are subjected to cyclic tension and compression loading, but also long-term, relaxation and progressive load tests are performed [6].

A new device was built up to enable the fibre pull-out test on single fibre model composites at high strain rates. In this work the single fibre pull-out test at high-speed loading is used to investigate the interphase behaviour of model composites of PVA fibres in cementitious matrix under impact loading in comparison with quasi-static loading.

2 Experimental

2.1 Material

For the investigation polyvinyl alcohol (PVA, Kuraray Co., Ltd., Kuralon K-II REC15) fibres with a diameter of 38 μm have been used. In order to change the fibre-matrix bond behaviour the finish of the PVA fibres was removed by

extraction for 8 hours in ethanol following 8 hours in n-hexan. Fig. 1 shows the PVA fibres in the initial state (a) and after extraction (b). For the cementitious matrix a concrete composition was used that is typically applied in strain-hardening cement-based composites [1]. A combination of Portland cement 42.5 R and fly ash was used as binder. The aggregate was quartz sand with a particle size ranging from 0.06-0.20 mm. Also a super plasticizer (Glenium ACE 30) and a viscosity agent have been used in the concrete matrix.

Fig.1. SEM images of PVA fibres in the initial state (a) and after extraction (b).

2.2 Single fibre pull-out

In order to prepare homogeneous single fibre model composites, the fibres were end-

embedded using an equipment constructed at the Leibniz Institute of Polymer Research [2]. The fibres were embedded in the concrete matrix using a length of either 1000 or 1500 µm, respectively, at 23°C ambient temperature and at a relative humidity of 50 %. After 24 h the specimens are transferred to a desiccator and stored for 28 days at a relative humidity of 90 %.

A specialized single fibre pull-out testing apparatus was used to conduct quasi-static investigations, the development of which is described in detail elsewhere [2]. The quasi-static pull-out tests were carried out at a pull-out speed of 0.01 µm/s. To perform high-speed pull-out tests a new equipment was built up using a piezo actuator (P 216.90, Physik Instrumente & Co. KG, Germany) that enables a pull-out speed of 10 000 µm/s and a maximum displacement of 180 µm. For this reason the complete force-displacement curve for the embedded length of more than 1000 µm can not be registered. The software program uses a data collection frequency of 100 kHz. For statistic reasons at least 15 samples were tested at each speed level. Based on the displacement rate and the embedded fibre length of 1000 µm, the average strain rate of the quasi-static pull-out test was approximately 10^{-5} s^{-1} , whereas the strain rate of the high speed pull-out tests is about 10^3 s^{-1} . The fibre fracture surface was investigated using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, Zeiss Ultra plus, Germany).

2.3 Interfacial parameters

In the single fibre pull-out test the fibre is sheared from the matrix and the force required to produce such shear is measured and interpreted in terms of interfacial strength. The mean interfacial shear strength τ_d is calculated along the entire fibre-matrix interface at the moment, when the external force, F_{\max} , applied to the fibre reaches its maximum. At the same time, the fibre-matrix debonding process is

completed. Hence, the mean interfacial shear strength is defined as:

$$\tau_d = \frac{F_{\max}}{\pi d_f l_e} \quad (1)$$

where, l_e is the embedded length and d_f the fibre diameter. The τ_d values calculated from equation 1 will be used in this work to distinguish between the quality of bond strength and to estimate the efficiency of fibre surface modification. However, it is well-known, that a quantitative characterization of the fibre-matrix interface properties requires a more adequate approach taking into account the local interfacial parameters instead of averaged ones as well as a separation of the contributions of adhesion and friction [3].

Fig. 2. Typical force-displacement recorded during a pull-out test

A typical force-displacement curve is shown in Fig. 2. It consists of three parts corresponding to three stages of a pull-out test. The first stage is defined from $0 \leq F \leq F_d$. At this stage the fibre-matrix interface remains intact and the curve is nearly linear. When the external load reaches a critical value (debonding force F_d), the fibre begins to debond off the matrix through interfacial crack propagation [7, 8]. At the second stage ($F_d \leq F \leq F_{\max}$) the force increases with the fibre end displacement (or with crack length). Frictional load in debonded regions is

added to the adhesional load from the intact part of the interface. After a peak load (F_{\max}) is reached, the crack propagation becomes unstable and the whole embedded length completely debonds leading to a sudden and drastically decrease of the measured force. From this moment and until the complete pull-out the force is due to frictional interaction between the fibre and the matrix. When the force reaches a minimum value (F_{stop}) the pull-out test is finished and the real embedded length is determined.

Using a cementitious matrix the debonding force F_d can not be clearly determined, so that only F_{\max} is used for characterization. The work during the first two stages of fibre pull-out is defined as debonding work W_d (equation 2). The total work W_{total} that is carried out by the system is determined as shown in equation 4. Because the maximum fibre displacement s for high speed tests is limited by the piezo actuator, the complete pull-out curve is not registered. For that reason, the total work W_{total} can only be determined for quasi-static but not for high-speed pull-out tests. In order to compare the pull-out work during both tests, another work (W_{150} , equation 4) was defined ranging from $F=0$ to the force at the maximum displacement that is used in the high-speed pull-out test being around $150 \mu\text{m}$.

$$W_d = \int_0^{F_{\max}} F ds \quad (2)$$

$$W_{\text{total}} = \int_{F_{\max}}^{F_{\text{stop}}} F ds \quad (3)$$

$$W_{150} = \int_0^{F_{150}} F ds \quad (4)$$

3 Results and Discussion

For the PVA fibres tested under quasi-static load two characteristic curves have been identified: (i) the complete fibre pull-out with typical force-displacement curve (Fig. 3, solid,

grey line) and (ii) an increasing force during pull-out up to fibre failure (Fig. 3, dotted grey line). The amount of completely pulled out fibres with 12 % is clearly lower than the amount of broken fibres with 87 %. The failure occurred at different displacements ranging from 200 to 600 μm in the force range of 500-800 mN. This value corresponds to one third of the average fibre strength that has been determined by single fibre tensile test with 1499 ± 189 MPa (gauge length 1 mm, testing velocity 180 mm/min). The increase of the force during pull-out does not necessarily result in fibre failure (Fig. 4). Plastic deformation and shearing-off of fibre parts was identified by SEM as a reason for the rising pull-out force (Fig. 5).

Fig.3. Force-displacement curves of PVA fibre/concrete pull-out (embedded length: 1000 μm) at quasi-static (pull-out speed $v=0.01$ $\mu\text{m/s}$) and high speed load (pull-out speed $v=10\ 000$ $\mu\text{m/s}$).

At high-speed loading the interfacial shear strength τ_d is twice as high compared to quasi-static loading (Fig. 6, embedded length: 1000 μm) due to the strong increase of F_{max} (Fig. 3). After debonding at the beginning of the curve in many cases the force increases again due to plastic deformation on the fibre surface. Although the force during the high speed pull-out test ranges on a higher level a fibre breakage of only 17 % was registered.

Fig. 4: Damaged top of a PVA fibre after shearing during quasi-static pull-out

Fig. 5. Sheared off surface of a PVA fibre during high-speed pull-out

Fig. 6. Interfacial shear strength τ_d of PVA fibres in the initial and the extracted state with an embedded length of 1000 μm and 1500 μm , respectively

Although the F_{max} and hence τ_d values are much higher at high-speed loading the debonding work W_d (Fig. 7) shows just a slight difference being 4.1 ± 2.4 and 4.9 ± 2.1 mNmm for quasi-static and high-speed loading, respectively. The work W_{150} up to a displacement of $150 \mu\text{m}$ is significantly higher for high-speed with 40.1 ± 10.5 compared with 25.1 ± 9.8 mNmm at quasi-static pull-out.

In literature the challenge of using PVA fibres in cementitious matrices is found in the development of very strong chemical bonds due to the hydroxyl groups in the molecular chains. The strong chemical interaction is responsible for the tendency of fibre rupture and a limited strain capacity of the reinforced matrix [9]. Li et al. [9] applied a fibre coating based on an oiling agent to control the interface properties with the aim of a reduced fibre-matrix bond leading to an improved tensile strain capacity of cementitious composites. In order to get deeper insight into the failure behaviour at high strain rates the fibre-matrix bond was changed by extraction of the PVA fibre finish. It was expected by literature studies to achieve an increased chemical interaction; however, the extraction of the fibre finish leads to decreased interfacial shear strength. Fig. 6 shows that τ_d is significantly reduced for extracted fibres in comparison with fibres in the initial state at embedded lengths of $1000 \mu\text{m}$. The amount of fibre breakage decreases to 11 % for quasi-static and zero for high-speed pull-out tests, respectively. The debonding work W_d of the extracted fibres is strongly decreased compared to the fibres in the initial state (Fig. 7); being 1.05 ± 0.95 at quasi-static and 1.85 ± 1.80 at high-speed loading, respectively. Also the work up to a displacement of $150 \mu\text{m}$ W_{150} is reduced in general compared to the initial fibre, however, higher values of W_{150} have been determined at high-speed (26.13 ± 8.18) compared to quasi-static loading (14.96 ± 5.54).

Fig. 7. Debonding work W_d of PVA fibres in the initial and the extracted state with an embedded length of $1000 \mu\text{m}$ and $1500 \mu\text{m}$, respectively

Fig.8. Force-displacement curves (up to a displacement of $150 \mu\text{m}$) of PVA fibre/concrete pull-out (embedded length: $1500 \mu\text{m}$) at a) quasi-static (pull-out speed $v=0.01 \mu\text{m/s}$) and b) high speed load (pull-out speed $v=10\,000 \mu\text{m/s}$).

To gain further knowledge about the failure behaviour of the PVA fibre in cementitious matrix the embedded length was increased from 1000 to $1500 \mu\text{m}$. The beginning of the force-displacement curves including the complete debonding process are shown in Fig. 8. Under quasi-static conditions higher debonding forces are registered again for the finished fibres compared to the extracted ones (see also Fig. 6). However, during the debonding process instead of only one maximum peak multiple peaks are revealed. A similar behaviour during debonding

was found for the high-speed pull-out testing, where at least two peaks have been determined for each sample independent on the state of the fibre surface. Furthermore, the state of the fibre surface does only influence the interfacial shear strength τ_d as well as W_d and W_{150} under quasi-static conditions. At high-speed testing similar values for τ_d , W_d and W_{150} are found for fibres in the initial state and after extraction (for the calculation of the W_d values the highest peak during debonding was used). In comparison to the embedded fibre length of 1000 μm the interfacial shear strength is generally reduced with increased embedded length, in particular for the fibres in the initial state at high-speed loading.

4 Conclusions

Single fibre model composites made of PVA fibres in a cementitious matrix are highly strain rate sensitive systems. This was shown by pull-out tests under quasi-static and high-speed loading for finished and extracted PVA fibres with an embedded fibre length of 1000 μm . The extraction of the fibre finish results in a lower fibre-matrix bond, however, the sensitivity to the strain rate remained as well as the failure behaviour. Higher embedded fibre lengths led to a changed debonding behaviour indicated by multiple peaks on a lower force level. Fibres with an embedded length of 1000 μm debond continuously from the matrix resulting in one maximum force peak. The increase of the embedded length to 1500 μm leads to a discontinuous, stepwise debonding resulting in lower forces and less sensitivity towards both, the fibre surface state and the strain rate. A discontinuous debonding strongly decreases the fibre surface area that contributes to the fibre-matrix bond. Therefore, the fibre material itself becomes dominating the pull-out behaviour.

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